

Brown planthopper (BPH) dispersal range under natural conditions in the Philippines

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Methods for measuring the movement of insect pests frequently require manipulating the insects in ways that may bias results. A fortuitous natural experiment in 1981-83 permitted a quantitative estimate of the dispersal range of BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* that avoided this difficulty.

As part of a larger study of the regional dynamics of rice-feeding insects, small kerosene light traps were established across a 17,000-ha area of irrigated, double-cropped rice in Nueva Ecija Province, Philippines. In early Feb 1982, large catches of BPH were noticed in the traps. The numbers caught declined from west to east.

At that time of year, many fields were still being prepared for the dry season crop or had been planted no more than 2 wk earlier. The only possible source of insects was an area of abandoned ricefields along the Chico River, dominated by volunteer rice and *Leersia hexandra*. (Farmers had cultivated the poorly drained area during a time when irrigation had been cut off for canal maintenance.)

Figure 1 illustrates the relationship between catches 6-25 Feb and distance from the old ricefields for the 16 sites in the northern half of the study area. An exponential decay fits the data well ($r = -0.92$, $P < 0.001$).

After correcting for the possible immigration from other sources of the 2.5 BPH/trap (estimated from the catch over the 20 d prior to 6 Feb) in the two traps farthest from the old fields, and after integrating and rotating the curve about the origin, I calculated that 50% of dispersing BPH would move less than 2.3 km, 80% less than 4.1 km, and 95% less than 6.5 km.

These estimates assume that dispersal is similar in all directions, which at first seems unlikely. Fifteen of the 16 light trap sites lay between north-northeast and

east of the old fields. To reach them, BPH would have had to fly directly into the prevailing winds (at that time, north-east to east between dusk and dawn).

Catches at the one site that lay downwind of the old fields (circled points in Fig. 1) however, were not notably higher than expected on the basis of the overall regression.

Could BPH have flown such considerable distances upwind? One possibility is that insects were avoiding take-off in strong winds, and that they made repeated flights, particularly near dawn when winds were lighter. These behaviors are known from the literature. Figure 2 supports this interpretation: the median catch in the 6-25 Feb period is seen to occur later in the sites farthest from the old ricefields ($r_s = 0.47$, $P < 0.05$). Note that at the downwind site, the median is reached 2 d later than the closer sites, suggesting that BPH may take more than one night to reach points only a few km away, whether upwind or downwind. ■

1. BPH catches in light traps over the period 6-25 Feb 1982 in relation to distance from Laon, an old-field area. $\ln Y = 9.939 - 0.7340 x$, $n = 32$ traps. Circled data = downwind locations.

2. Date of median catch in the 6-25 Feb period in relation to distance from Laon, an old-field area. $n = 14$ sites.

Integrated pest management-weeds

Ricefield weeds in Chitwan Valley, Nepal

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Rice is the main crop in Chitwan Valley in the central inner Terai of Nepal, about 145 km south of Kathmandu. We surveyed the weeds in transplanted ricefields and determined their dominance Aug-Sep 1987-88.

Fifty weeds were identified (see table). On the basis of Sculthop's life-form categories, the weed flora was composed of 49 emergent weeds and one floating-

Scientific name and summed dominance ratio (SDR) of weeds^a in transplanted ricefields, Chitwan Valley, Nepal.

Scientific name	SDR value ^b
<i>Eleocharis atropurpurea</i> (Retz.) Presl	12.577
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm. f.) Presl	10.534
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	7.958
<i>Ludwigia perennis</i> L.	7.207
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	6.802
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl	5.934
<i>Rotala indica</i> (Willd.) Koehne	4.770
<i>Sagittaria guayanensis</i> Kunth ^a	3.398
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R. Br. ex Roem & Schult.	3.220
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i> Gaertn.	3.098
<i>Scirpus lateriflorus</i> Gmel.	2.705
<i>Caesulia axillaris</i> Roxb.	2.668
<i>Eriocaulon cinereum</i> R. Br.	2.697
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	2.482
<i>Commelina paludosa</i> B1.	1.718
<i>Cyanotis cristata</i> D. Don	1.705
<i>Ageratum houstonianum</i> Mill.	1.618
<i>Hedyotis diffusa</i> L.	1.528
<i>Ceratopteris thalictroides</i> (L.) Brogn.	1.337
<i>Tenagocharis latifolia</i> (D. Don) Buch.	1.280
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	1.242
<i>Phyllanthus urinaria</i> L.	1.072
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	0.968
<i>Cyperus squarrosus</i> L.	0.795
<i>Cyperus compressus</i> L.	0.750
<i>Lindernia procumbens</i> (Krock.) Philcox	0.735
<i>Lindernia anagallis</i> (Burm. f.) Pennell	0.724
<i>Eragrostis tenella</i> (L.) Beauv. ex Roem. & Schult.	0.662
<i>Murdannia nudiflora</i> (L.) Brenan	0.631
<i>Lindernia ciliata</i> (Colsm.) Pennell	0.571
<i>Amisophacelus axillaris</i> Rolla Rao & Kamathy	0.534
<i>Phyllanthus fraternus</i> Webster	0.467
<i>Scirpus juncooides</i> Roxb.	0.448
<i>Melochia concatenata</i> L.	0.434

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